

The Szymanowski connection, Górecki as a grand-student.

Musical connections between Henryk Górecki and Karol Szymanowski.

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In this Essay I hope to examine the complex relationship between Karol Szymanowski (b.3 October 1882, d. 28 March 1937) and his contemporary Henryk Górecki (b. December 6 1933, d. November 12, 2010) born 51 years later. I also hope to explore the link that Bolesław Szabelski provided as Szymanowski's student and later as Górecki's teacher. I also hope to complete an analysis of Górecki's *Symphony no.3 Op. 36* (1976) and compare it to aspects of Szymanowski's *Stabat Mater* (1926).

Karol Szymanowski's Poland

The Beginnings

In many ways the birth of Ukraine born composer Karol Szymanowski (1882-1937) is often hailed as a rebirth of Polish music after Chopin, and, indeed, as hailing a beginning of Polish contemporary music.

The historical context for the beginning and growth of modern Polish music can be seen largely in the context of European post-nationalistic trends in western art music.

As composers were becoming more interested in exploring more complicated idioms that were less rooted in tradition at the end of the 19th century, an opening for a unique style influenced by French Impressionism, Slavic and North European folk music and Polish religiously inspired reflection was being formed by a group of young composers based in Warsaw at the turn of the 20th century. This group titled **Młoda Polska w Muzyce** (Young Poland in Music), formed in 1905 of the composers, Karol Szymanowski, Grzegorz Fitelberg, Ludomir Różycki and Apolinary Szeluto.

It was largely created as a reaction to the conservative musical scene in Warsaw and more directly as a reaction to the programming of the newly founded Warsaw Philharmonic, which was failing to

encourage the new progressive tastes of the compositional youth. However, Fin de siècle Poland was still hugely indebted to Chopin who was still considered a major figure in Polish music; heralded for the culture of salon music which he left behind.

It was at this time and under these circumstances that a young Szymanowski; although theoretically untrained, began composing his first piano pieces; Opus 1, *Nine Preludes for Piano* (1899) (see figure 1.1 of 1st prelude in b minor on the following 2 pages).

These pieces clearly show the early inspiration of Chopin and they even give a glimpse of the unique already maturing style which was to follow in Szymanowski's own work.

Szymanowski's nine preludes written from 1899 – 1900, around the time that he was 18, and first published by The Young Polish Composers publishing house (*Spółka Nakładowa Młodych Kompozytorów Polskich*) founded by Fitelberg and Różycki then subsequently published by Universal Edition Wien in 1906, remain some of the most astounding pieces of his output.

Not only are they readily approachable and aesthetically pleasing, (See Z. Jachimecki's quote below) but they also contain a subtle awareness of contemporary trends and indeed contain a certain aspect of refinement reminiscent of Chopin, harmonic turns akin to Scriabin¹, and an advanced chromaticism to match even that of R. Strauss or Wagner.

'The lyric sincerity of these works, the charmingly poetic ideas, the beauty of melodic invention, the harmonic variety and, finally, the elegance of technique and fineness of form, commanded universal admiration.'²

This quote taken from an essay by Zdzisław Jachimecki, translated by O.T. Kindler and published 16 years after the publication of the preludes shows a keen understanding of what music in Poland would have been like at this time, and of how the appearance of such an individual figure such as Karol Szymanowski would have caused much of a stir in the contemporary music camp.

¹ Anna Iwanicka-Nijakowska, 'Karol Szymanowski, *Nine Preludes for piano Op. 1*' (culture.pl, 2007)

² Zdzisław Jachimecki, *Karol Szymanowski* (The Musical Quarterly, Vol. 8, No. 1, January, 1922, p. 23)

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Prelude Nº I.

Karol Szymanowski Op. 1 Nº 1

Andante ma non troppo.

PIANO.

pp legato

dolce cantando ten.

p

ten.

rit.

pp

più f

cresc.

ten.

dim. riten.

ten.

ppp

dolce

Fig. 1.1

The musical score consists of six systems of piano accompaniment and a vocal line. The piano part is written in G major and 4/4 time. The vocal line is in the soprano register. The score includes various dynamics and tempo markings: *rall.*, *più p*, *poco agitato*, *poco - a -*, *poco - - - cre - scen - do*, *(poco meno mosso)*, *ff*, *a tempo*, *dim.*, *rit.*, *pp*, *rall.*, *e*, *dim.*, and *ppp*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. The piece concludes with a fermata and a *ppp* dynamic marking.

U. E. 8852. 8853.

Fig. 1.1. cont.

The key structures of each of the preludes are as follows.

Prelude, Key

I, b minor IV, b flat minor VII, c minor

II, d minor V, d minor VIII, e flat minor

III, D flat major VI, a minor IX, b flat minor

The first prelude in b minor exhibits a hushed and restrained lyricism, broad melodic phrases, acute and clever harmonic turns, and a two-triplet harmonic underpinning in the bass.

Soft b minor thematic tonalities swing to subdominant e minor resolutions as chromatic turns harmonically blur the bass leading to the key of c# minor and beyond. These gradually become more harmonically complicated, yet still retain an audibly coherent flow and display a loyalty to the theme, all quite unique qualities for the compositionally untrained youth of 18.

Karol Szymanowski ³

The next step for Szymanowski was to be a focus on vocal works.

Szymanowski's relationship with poetry and more importantly with song began with his work *Sześć Pieśni/Six Songs* Op. 2 (1909) written for piano and voice on the poetry of Kazimierz Tetmajer,

³Karol Szymanowski, Polish Music Information Centre (2002-2008).

composed between 1900 – 1902.

The titles for each of the songs are as follows.

- The world has been left afar.
- You have not died.
- In the fog.
- Sometimes when half – dreaming.
- I heard you.
- The Pilgrim.

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These settings exhibit much of the same harmonic considerations as his preludes, but still seem fresh in contrast. However, his treatment of the voice leaves a lot to be desired as it appears nowhere as fluent as his technique of writing for the piano. Nevertheless, this Opus 2 set the way for many song-based compositions to come, exhibiting a fondness for the voice both as solo and in chorus.

A fondness shared in much later choral orchestral works such as *Stabat Mater* Op. 53 (1925-26) for solo soprano, alto, baritone, mixed chorus and orchestra on the medieval latin poem translated into Polish by Józef Jankowski and indeed, also in his *Symphony number 3: Pieśń o nocy/The Song of the Night*, Op. 27 (1914) for solo tenor and orchestra in which he sets Tadeusz Miciński's translation of a poem on the same title by a thirteenth century Persian poet named Jalaluddin Rumi.

Szymanowski's *Stabat Mater* is often seen as the culmination of his artistic career. Finished in 1926 and performed in 1929, this intensely expressive work set to the text of the weeping mother Mary for her son, a text so often set by other Slavic composers such as Penderecki, Schaeffer and even Dvořák. It evokes a certain mysticism that is often attributed to composers of later generations.

With modalities that stretch as far back as early medieval chant and as forward as the fluid tonalities of Debussy and the luminous harmonies as contemporary as the composition itself.

⁴ Anon/Organisation, 'Composers, Karol Szymanowski', Polish Music Information Centre. (2002-2008)

Szymanowski's position in the Polish music scene at the time was seen as more of a savour like figure, than a mere reiteration of past trends.

Zdzislaw Jachimecki in his aforementioned essay suggests many important harmonic connections between Szymanowski and other figures, more notably connections with that of experiments with dissonance in his vocal music, experiments even rivalling that of the major figures of present and previous times.

'He outdid all the experiments of his contemporaries. Wagner, Hugo Wolf, Richard Strauss, Reger, Debussy, even Scriabin and Schonberg, who at that time were, comparatively speaking, quite modest in their use of dissonances, were surpassed in these songs of Szymanowski's.'⁵

The songs which the author refers to are Szymanowski's *Twelve Songs* Op. 17 written after his first symphony and at the time when he was living in Berlin. These show somewhat of a progression from the earlier lyrically modal style into a style more up to date, one akin to that of his contemporaries.

Another interesting stylistic point of attention to be found in his music is his affection for impressionistic colours. After spending the early summer of 1914 in Paris he came into contact with the picture sound worlds of Debussy, Ravel and late Scriabin. These influences can be clearly seen in his *Métopes* Op. 29 (1915) for piano and in the *Mythes* Op. 30 (also 1915) for Violin and Piano. These pieces which are quite daring both in their rhythmic and melodic content also show aspects of Szymanowski's varied influences gathered from the exotic tableaux of Sicily and North Africa which he visited before staying in Paris.

In his later period his interest in dissonance and strange (uncommon at the time) modulations grew substantially, this interest is evident in most of his later instrumental works for example his *Third Piano Sonata* Op. 36 (1917).

⁵ Zdzislaw Jachimecki, p28.

It is true that Szymanowski set the tone of generations to come, not only influencing the music of his students but successfully creating an important influence into a wider spectrum, an importance shared with his succeeding Polish composers. He undoubtedly influenced the lush film and sonorous art music of Wojciech Kilar, the sonoristic blocks and aurally striking extended technique use of Penderecki, and the rich soundscapes and stark archaic, adapted folk melodies of Henryk Górecki's later 'Reflective' period.

It was under this influence that the composer and organist Bolesław Szabelski under Szymanowski's tutelage in Warsaw from (1927-29) gradually found his compositional path. A path heavily influenced by Neoclassicism (Szabelski was particularly fond of Stravinski's early ballet scores and this can be seen in his *Orchestral study* [1938]).⁶

Bolesław Szabelski was born in Radoryż near the town of Łuków in eastern Poland on the 3rd of December 1896. He studied piano and organ at the Warsaw music society 1908-1913, then studying organ under Mieczysław Surzyńskiego from 1913, and going on to participate as a soloist in Felix Guilmant's organ symphony with the Warsaw Philharmonic Orchestra. It was there in Warsaw after studying with Roman Statkowski 1923-25, that he began his studies with Szymanowski in 1927.

⁶Adrian Thomas, *'Polish music since Szymanowski'* (p. 14)

Bolesław Szabelski ⁷

Although not quite as successful as Szymanowski in his lasting compositional influence, he was very successful in teaching, achieving many state honours. From 1945 he worked as the Dean of Pedagogical studies in the state academy of music in Katowice, moving to the position of chair of composition in 1957 and then, subsequently achieving the title of Professor in 1958. It was in this academy that he began teaching Henryk Mikołaj Górecki.

Henryk Mikołaj Górecki was born on the 6th of December 1933 on the Górecki family farm near the town of Czernica in upper Silesia in present Poland. He was seen to have inherited his mother's musical ability but was largely discouraged by his father to play his mother's piano. However, later on his father sent him to Pavel Hajduga for group violin lessons. He then went on to teacher training college in Rybnik and then after studying full time in Rybnik went to apply for studies at the Higher school of Music in Katowice where he came under Szabelski's tutelage.

Górecki's relationship to Bolesław Szabelski was one of shared enthusiasm for Szymanowski and although, initially Szabelski's influence on Górecki can be seen as minimal (Szabelski gave Górecki a lot of compositional freedom), a certain refinement of Górecki's early Neoclassical works such as *Sonata for two Violins* (1957) can be seen as being related to Szabelski's own direction at that time.

⁷ Bolesław Szabelski, Polish Music Information centre (2002-2008).

Szabelski's influence on Górecki then grew during the period of the high Polish Avant-Garde of the late 1950s with Szabelski holding a greater stake in his pupil's development (Górecki graduating with distinction in 1960). More than a small mutual influence can be seen in both composers' serialist works at this time, with both sharing strong expressive pointillistic Weberian techniques. Szabelski's *Verses* (1961) and Górecki's *Scontri* (1960) can be seen as direct siblings to each other in this respect. Górecki leading in his use of free intuitive serialism, with carefully planned out procedures which were used until they fulfilled their purpose and then continuing on as he saw fit. However, an even more important point is the relationship of Górecki's early works to the later ones of Szymanowski, strongly alluding to *Stabat Mater's* opening theme in his *Variations* Op. 4 (1956) for Violin and Piano ⁸. It was later on, after his *Symphony No. 2 'Copernican'* Op.31, that a dramatic musical change can be heard, more directed toward the 'Eternal' and less rooted in the prevalent western academic tradition. The *Symphony no. 3* (1976), in this vein, being one of his most important works stylistically.

Henryk Mikołaj Górecki⁹

⁸ Adrian Thomas, '*Górecki, Oxford Studies of Composers*', (p.2)

⁹Henryk Mikołaj Górecki, Polish Music Centre, University of Southern California (1999- 2001).

Górecki's various compositional styles/trends can be divided into three relatively distinct periods;

Student Neoclassical works 1955/56, including:
(Important works are written in **Bold**)

Four Preludes op. 1 for piano * (1955)

Toccata op. 2 for two pianos * (1955)

Three Songs op. 3 for medium voice and piano * (1956)

***Variations op. 4* for violin and piano * (1956)**

Quartettino op. 5 for two flutes, oboe and violin * (1956)

Sonatina in One Part op. 8 for violin and piano * (1956)

From a Bird's Nest op. 9a for piano (1956)

Lullaby op. 9 for piano (1956, 1980)

Two Songs to words by Federico Garcia Lorca op. 42 for medium voice and piano (1956, 1980)

Avant Garde, late 1950s-60's works including:

***Sonata for piano no. 1 op. 6* (1956, 1990)**

Various Pieces op. 52 for piano (1956-61,19)

***Sonata for Two Violins op. 10* * (1957)**

Concerto for five instruments and string quartet op. 11 * (1957)

Epitaph op. 12 for mixed choir and instrumental ensemble * (1958)

Five Pieces op. 13 for two pianos * (1959)

***Symphony No. 1 "1959" op. 14* for string orchestra and percussion * (1959)**

Three Diagrams op. 15 for solo flute * (1959)

***Songs of Joy and Rhythm op. 7* for two pianos and chamber orchestra * (1959-60,19)**

Monologhi op. 16 for soprano and three instrumental groups * (1960)

***Scontri op. 17* for orchestra * (1960)**

Diagram IV op. 18 for solo flute (1961)

Chorale in the Canon Form for string quartet (1961, 1984)

***Genesis – I. Elementi op. 19 no. 1 per tre archi* * (1962)**

***Genesis – II. Canti strumentali op. 19 no. 2 per 15 esecutori* * (1962)**

***Genesis – III. Monodramma op. 19 no. 3 per soprano, metalli di percussione e sei violbassi* * (1963)**

and the works which constitute the biggest and still growing part of his career, the modal, folk inflected period of reserved expression, more influenced by Szymanowski's 'Polish period':

***Three Pieces in the Old Style* for string orchestra * (1963)**

Choros I op. 20 per strumenti ad arco * (1964)

Refrain op. 21 for orchestra * (1965)

***Little Music I op. 22* for two trumpet and guitar (1967)**

***Little Music II op. 23* for 4 trumpets, 4 trombones, 2 pianos and percussion * (1967)**

***Little Music III op. 25* for violas * (1967)**

Old Polish Music op. 24 for brass instruments and strings * (1967-69)
*Cantata op. 26 for organ * (1968)*
*Canticum graduum op. 27 for orchestra * (1969)*
Little Music IV “Trombone Concerto” op. 28 for clarinet, trombone, cello and piano * (1970)
Ad Matrem op. 29 for solo soprano, mixed choir and orchestra * (1971)
Two Sacred Songs op. 30 for solo baritone and orchestra (1971)
Two Sacred Songs op. 30bis for solo baritone and orchestra (1971)
Symphony No. 2 “Copernican” op. 31 for solo soprano and baritone, mixed choir and orchestra * (1972)
*Two Songs op. 33 for a choir of 4 equal voices * (1972)*
*Euntes ibant et flebant op. 32 for mixed a cappella choir * (1972-73)*
*Three Dances op. 34 for symphony orchestra * (1973)*
Amen op. 35 for mixed a cappella choir * (1975)
Symphony No. 3 “Symphony of Sorrowful Songs” op. 36 for solo soprano and orchestra * (1976)
*Three Little Pieces op. 37 for violin and piano * (1977)*
Beatus vir op. 38 - psalm for solo baritone, mixed choir and great orchestra * (1979)
Wide Water op. 39 for mixed a cappella choir (1979)
*Concerto for harpsichord (or piano) and string orchestra op. 40 * (1980)*
Mazurkas op. 41 for piano (1980)
Blessed Raspberry Songs op. 43 for voice and piano (1980)
Dark Evening Falls op. 45, five folk songs for mixed a cappella choir (1981)
*My Grey Vistula op. 46, folk song for mixed a cappella choir * (1981)*
Miserere op. 44 for mixed a cappella choir * (1981-87)
Lullabies and Dances op. 47 for violin and piano (1982)
*O Domina Nostra op. 55 – Meditations on Our Lady of Jasna Góra for solo soprano and organ * (1982-85,19)*
Songs to words by Juliusz Słowacki op. 48 for voice and piano (1983)
Oh, My Lavender Wreath op. 50, seven folk songs for mixed a cappella choir (1984)
Cloud Is Coming, Rain Is Falling op. 51, five folk songs for mixed a cappella choir (1984)
*Recitativos and Ariosos “Lerchenmusik” op. 53 for clarinet, cello and piano * (1984, 1986)*
Three Lullabies op. 49 for mixed a cappella choir (1984, 1991)
Marian Songs op. 54, five songs for mixed a cappella choir (1985)
Under Your Care op. 56, Marian song for 8-part mixed a cappella choir (1985)
For the Angelus Bells Are Ringing op. 57 for mixed a cappella choir (1986)
*For You, Anne-Lill op. 58 for flute and piano * (1986, 1990)*
*Aria (operatic scene) op. 59 for tuba, piano, tam-tam and great drum * (1987)*
Totus Tuus op. 60 for mixed a cappella choir * (1987)
Come Holy Spirit op. 61 for mixed a cappella choir (1988)
*It Is Already Dusk. String Quartet No. 1 op. 62 * (1988)*
Good Night op. 63 for soprano, alto flute, 3 tam-tams and piano * (1988-90)
Intermezzo for piano (1990)
Quasi una fantasia. String Quartet No. 2 op. 64 (1990-91)

Concerto-Cantata op. 65 for solo flute and orchestra * (1991-92)

***Little Requiem for a Certain Polka op. 66 (Kleines Requiem für eine Polka)* for piano and 13 instruments (1993)**

Piece for String Quartet (1993)

By the Window, By Mine for voice and piano (1995)

Three Fragments to words by Stanisław Wyspiański op. 69 for voice and piano (1995-96)

Valentine Piece for flute and bell (1996)

Little Fantasy op. 73 for violin and piano (1997)

Salve Sidus Polonorum. Cantata About St Adalbert op. 72 for great mixed choir, two pianos, organ and percussion ensemble (1997-2000)

Hey, Downhill, Dun Horse, five regional Kurpie songs for a cappella choir (1999)

String Quartet No. 3 (1999-2005)

Lobgesang op. 76 for mixed choir and orchestral bells (2000)

May They Live and Sing for Us for vocal ensemble (2000)

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However, for the purpose of this essay I am going limit myself by comparing aspects of Szymanowski's *Stabat Mater* with an analysis of Górecki's *Symphony no.3 "Symphony of Sorrowful Songs"* Op. 36.

Analysis of Górecki's *Symphony Number 3, "Symphony of Sorrowful Songs"*

Movement I

The first movement of the symphony opens with the second section of the Double Bass' murmuring a pianissimo 24 bar long adapted liturgical theme in the key of E Aeolian in 2/4 time.

This theme is used as the subject for a canon which takes up the majority of the first movement, . A theme that I will label A.

With diatonic, canonic entries at the interval of a fifth every 24 bars at a bar's length to each other, a canon builds up within the 8 different voices of the *divisi* strings. As the voices enter diatonically there is a layering of modes beginning with the 2nd double basses on E aeolian (bar 1), 1st double basses on B phrygian (bar 26), 2nd cellos on F# locrian (b. 51), 1st cellos on C lydian (b. 76), 2nd violas on G ionian (b. 101), 1st violas on D mixolydian (b. 126), 2nd violins on A dorian (b. 151) and finally reaching E aeolian again on bar 176 in the 1st violins.

¹⁰ Henryk Górecki, Polish Music Information centre (2002-2008).

This results in a brilliant 8-part polyphonic crescendo effect from the 2nd double basses to the 1st violins. After the height of the canon the voices gradually turn to octave doublings of the theme in their respective sections and the texture is thinned out. The theme can be clearly heard in five part polyphony; beginning with the 2nd violins 8va doubling on A dorian in bar 199, 1st violins 8va doubling on E aeolian (bar 200), double bass unison on B phrygian (b. 218), 1st violins unison on E aeolian (b. 224) cellos unison on C lydian (b. 244), 2nd violins unison on A dorian (b. 247), 2nd violas unison on G ionian with cellos unison (b. 273), and violas unison on G ionian with cellos (b. 293). In bar 293 the double basses drop out. 1st and 2nd violins unison on E aeolian in bar 294.

Leaving a two-voice canon evident in bar 295. In bar 317 all voices land on a sustained unison E which is held into the next section (B) beginning on the first beat of bar 321.

This section begins in 4/4 with a unison accented E in the piano and harp, this accent, which can be viewed as representing a gong or bell effect (used similarly in Russian Orthodox music) leads the listener into a sense of expectation. In bar 326 the solo soprano enters for the first time with the word “Synku” beginning the fifteenth century lament of the holy cross. This is doubled with the 1st violins and the flutes and there is a layering effect here within the strings and flutes, as one voice rises to the next pitch it becomes stationary and is held on as a higher voice takes over the melodic ascension. The resulting tone cluster (E, F#, G & A) hardly seems noticeable at all but there is an definitely an audible stir of tension present in the effect. This section continues until bar 339 where the texture is once again hinged on the note E. The Bassoon, Contra-bassoon and Horns produce a pedal E over which another rising motif in the *divisi* strings is heard, leaving the lower voice to stay on E and the upper one to ascend with the melodic line of the voice. Here is another example of the layering effect. The tonality here is noticeably different with the absence of the F# of the previous section and leans towards the G mixolydian mode. The strings then ascend in block chords with the 1st section of the 1st violins doubling the soprano at pitch. In bar 343 the description *Appassionato* ushers a large block texture with the horns and trombones doubling the cellos and violas. There is a return of F# in bar 347 as a passing note in the soprano line. In bar 348 is a sustained G major chord

in 2nd inversion which acts as a respite from the previous section. Bar 350 sees a change of mood to *Affettuoso*. There is also a key change to the mode of A flat mixolydian in the key of D flat major, with a string cluster beginning on A flat in the 2nd cellos reaching up to C natural in the 1st section of the 1st violins, as the 1st section of the violins move upwards with the voice as the 2nd section of the 2nd violins down to the 2nd section of the cellos descend their cluster to G flat in the next bar. This expansion and contraction of stepwise movement continues until bar 358 where a chord of D major signals a change in tonality cancelling out the flats of before leaving only F#. This section entitled *Lamentoso* leads on to a gradual crescendo beginning in bar 362 on a pedal E as before with an ascending *Doloroso* vocal line creates the anticipation of climax which is reached in bar 369. This climax is enhanced by the reappearance of the canon (again in 2/4), this time beginning at its highest point in the 1st violins reaching all the way down to the double basses in the dynamic of fortissimo. The revisit of the canon (A1) gradually winds its way down, with the texture thinning using unison doublings and drones on E signalling the end of a unison canonic line. This continues to the very bottom of the strings leading to the original theme in the 2nd section of the double basses in E aeolian at the very beginning. In bar 603 there is semitonal dissonance between E and F natural in the low strings and at the bottom range of the piano. This lasts for three 6/4 bars and resolves to an octave E in bar 606 which is held until the 1st beat of bar 608. There are then 5 beats of silence which mark the end of the 1st movement. The form of this movement can then be largely seen as being A, B, A1.

Movement II

This movement begins with the interval of a perfect fifth of A and E in *divisi* violins, violas and cellos, and piano and harp in the first bar of 2/4. The top E (after a quaver) then rises to G# over the A making a major seventh, the E is also sustained in other voices and strengthens the position of the A making the G# more noticeable, this lasts for one and a half beats in the time of Lento e Largo (marked in the score as crotchet equals 44 beats per minute).

In bar 2 the G# and E resolve to F# and D in the 1st violins as E and G# are sustained in the 2nd

violins, the resulting cluster contains the notes D, E, F#, G#, present in two interlocking 3rds between the violin sections. This tonality is mirrored to a lesser extent in the piano but with the piano having an octave's distance between its 'cluster'. This cluster lasts for four beats and contains the harmony for the first theme of A in this movement. This theme is then repeated a few times until its chord is held for 12 beats from bar 8 until 10.

In bar 11 the key changes to quite a dark B flat sonority (section B), a key often associated with evil and death in Russian culture. This chord in the clarinets, horns, piano and the low strings begins the vocal section of this movement with the text taken from a Gestapo cell in the mountain town of Zakopane in south-west Poland. The voice enters in bar 14 with the word 'Mamo' (Mother) on the D flat third of the chord above middle C and drops to middle C in the next bar, this C doubled in the 1st horns, clarinets, violas, cellos and double basses is sustained against the B flats creating a strong dissonance and sense of unrest. In the next bar the C rises back to D flat lifting the tension for a moment. This is repeated in bar 18 and 19 with the same orchestration. The next phrase of the voice features a momentary thickening of lower string texture in the 2nd basses, cellos and violas on the 3rd beat of bar 21, with the voice rising to E flat and then doing down by step to C again on the 3rd beat of the next bar (section B1). A longer phrase begins in bar 32 with the soprano moving in minims (doubled by the 1st section of the 1st violins) reaching B flat above middle C in bar 34. There is more thickening of string texture here in the violas, cellos, and basses where a build-up of diatonic chords with clustered seconds and thirds can be heard growing upwards to mirror the height of the voice. The only orchestration here is strings and soprano voice. This continues its ascent reaching A flat above the treble clef in bar 42, which is the highest note of the voice in the entire piece. This is accompanied by a dramatic crescendo which can be seen as the climax of the movement. There is then a mirror decrescendo until bar 45. This texture descends and thins out until bar 55 where there is a return of the A section in its original orchestration in bar 56. The voice is present this time and doubles the top voice of the 1st violins with the word 'Mamo'. This is repeated three times and ends on F# in bar 65 which changes enharmonically to G flat in the next bar. Thus,

returns the rising string cluster section (B) in the key of B flat minor in bar 66. Here the harp doubles the voice at pitch and at an octave and two octaves lower. In bar 85 the momentum slows and there is repetition of the B flat minor chords in the strings and harp.

The final section of 'Zdrowaś Mario' (Hail Mary) begins in bar 86, here the piano doubles the strings, and the harp keeps its repetition of D flat in three octaves. In bar 92 the momentum slows with the voice repeating treble clef D flats, under this a B flat minor chord is sustained for three bars in 2/4 time and subsequently held three times for two bars of 4/4. Then from bar 103 being sustained for 6 and a half bars until a bar and a half of silence is heard, the movement finishes at the end of bar 110. The form of this movement can be seen as being A, B, B1, A, B1.

Movement III

The third movement begins on the first beat of bar 1 with a three-note chord in the 2nd violins on the note (F), Violas (B) and Cellos (A). The inner voice B then resolves upwards by step on the next beat to a C, completing a 1st inversion chord of F major (the outer voices repeating their notes).

This points the tonality of the movement towards F lydian. This step movement continues with the rise and fall of the lydian fourth to the perfect fifth creating the tension in the next few bars. In bar 6 the violins enter with sustained high Es which are only interrupted by an accented E crotchet in the harps and piano. All of this characterising the A motif of the third movement.

In bar 13 there is a change of accent from the resolution being on the first beat dropping to the B on the second beat. In bar 20 the voice enters with an arrangement of a folk song from the Opole region in southern Poland about a mother who has lost her son in the first world war. This melody is doubled by the piccolos at an octave higher and by the flutes at pitch. The 2nd voice of the 1st violins then drops to double the note that the voice finishes each phrase on, being mainly E or A, this points the tonality towards A aeolian. In bar 49 a *pochissimo* crescendo leads the strings into a change of string texture marked with *Ben Tenuto* (A1) using signature triads of added sixths or inverted sevenths in this case A-C-E-F to B-C-E-G. In bar 56 the 2nd section of the 2nd violins drop to E above middle C adding a further thickness to the texture. Bar 59 sees the addition of the clarinets to

the flutes and piccolos doubling the soprano. In bar 71 there is the beginning of a crescendo, growing until bar 82 and falling away in bar 83. The stepwise rising theme (A) of the step from B to C heard before in bar 14 returns in the Piccolo, Flutes and Clarinets in a three-octave spread in bar 86. The violins open into a three octave E spread in bar 109 and this is sustained over the rest of the strings. Again, in bar 113, a *pochissimo* leads to a heightening in tension and mood with the first violins joining the rest of the strings in their stepwise movement up an octave in bar 115. In bar 152 there is a definite key change (this time explicit in the score) to A major with repeated A major chords in various inversions in the strings (B). This section ends in bar 235, and there is a grand pause (P.G.) marking in bar 236. Bar 237 features a return to the A theme at the beginning of the movement back in the home tonality. This changes in bar 249 with rising block triads this continues until bar 274 where the key once again changes to a glorious A major reiteration, of the A major triads in the strings and doubled by the piano, with the major third of C# being repeated each bar in the harp. In bar 282 the chord gradually descends through the notes finally reaching a low point in bar 289 with the highest note in all voices staying on C# just above middle C. This chord is repeated five times before settling on bar 294, this is held *senza dim* until the fifth beat of bar 396, there are then seven beats of silence before the movement ends at the end of bar 297. The form of the movement can then be seen as being A, A1, B.

Conclusion

The position of *Stabat Mater* Op. 53 in Karol Szymanowski's output is a very personal one, written for his deceased niece and officially dedicated to the patrons dead wife; Isabella Krystallowej, the work attempts to reflect the anguish of his sister (whom Szymanowski helped console afterwards) at her daughter's premature death. This reflection which is shared in the *Stabat Mater* text with the mother Mary for her son Jesus, depicts an intense maternal bond which results in emotional torture and grief for Mary, even asking to share in Jesus' pain.

Szymanowski's harmonic language in this piece is particularly pure and exhibits many restrictions much different from the exotic works of before, this piece is indeed said to be the peak of his

'Polish' period. In this work he uses triads in unconventional (modal) sequences, archaic open 5ths and medieval chant melody.

In relation to the *Stabat Mater's* use of folk modality, Jim Samson talks about how the rediscovery of native Polish folk music could have led to a marked change of direction in Szymanowski's music at that time.

'Szymanowski was at pains to distance himself from that 'exotic' use of folk music ('wild birds imprisoned in academic cages') that paved the way for more 'authentic' treatments, though he acknowledged its historical role. There is some irony in that. What he failed to say (and perhaps see) is that it was precisely the exoticism of the highland music that enabled a new direction in his own music.'¹¹

I believe some of the aspects of tonality and orchestration in Szymanowski's *Stabat Mater* can be related to Górecki's *Symphony No. 3*, such as use of folk modality, many present in *Stabat Mater's* resurrection of medieval chant modalities, and Górecki's use of all 7 in his symphony.

The topic of the maternal bond is also very prevalent in the Symphony with three songs directly related to motherhood, the first; a fifteenth century lament from the holy cross monastery.

The second; a prayer to the virgin Mary, written by an eighteen-year-old prisoner in the 'Palace' Gestapo jail in Zakopane in south west Poland. Finally, in the third movement, a folk song of a mother who has lost her son in the first world war. All of the songs about the pleading of or to a mother for salvation, reassurance and comfort, in the knowledge of the uniqueness of the eternal maternal bond.

The music of Karol Szymanowski and Henryk Górecki may be directly comparable in terms of style and historical influence, it is true that both Górecki and Szymanowski reverted back to a more free, expressive, pre-renaissance style with both trying to break free from the historical and political constraints that they faced at the beginning of the twentieth century and then later in its second half. A new turn was required, and I believe that through Szymanowski's lasting influence Henryk Górecki found the strength to write his third symphony and as a result was able to create a truly

¹¹ Samson, Jim, *Review, Selected Writings of Karol Szymanowski* (Music & Letters, p. 141)

unique and beautiful piece of music, which I believe will have lasting appeal for generations to come.

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